

1 COMPARISON OF THREE RAPID NON-DESTRUCTIVE TECHNIQUES COUPLED
2 WITH A CLASSIFIER TO INCREASE TRANSPARENCY IN THE SEAFOOD VALUE
3 CHAIN: BIOELECTRICAL IMPEDANCE ANALYSIS (BIA), NEAR-INFRARED
4 SPECTROSCOPY (NIR) AND TIME DOMAIN REFLECTOMETRY (TDR)

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16 **ABSTRACT**¹

17 Bioelectrical impedance analysis (BIA), near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopy and time domain
18 reflectometry (TDR) were compared as non-destructive techniques, coupled with a classifier
19 based on partial least square discriminant analysis (PLS-DA), to assess added water detection in
20 a seafood model: tuna. Three classification models were developed for each technology in

¹ **ABBREVIATIONS:** Internet of things (IoT), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR), partial least squares discriminant analysis (PLS-DA), bioelectrical impedance analysis (BIA), near infrared (NIR), time domain reflectometry (TDR), ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA), resistance (R), reactance (Xc), phase angle (Pa), standard normal variate detrend (SNVd), standard normal variate (SNV), multiplicative scatter correction (MSC), generalized least squares weighting (GLS Weighting), probabilistic quotient normalization (PQN), external parameter orthogonalization (EPO), cross-validation (CV), latent variables (LV), latent variable 1 (LV1), latent variable 2 (LV2).

21 unfrozen, thawed and in a combination of both stages to distinguish between added and non-
22 added water samples. Results were acceptable for the unfrozen stage with all the technologies,
23 giving TDR the best performance (accuracy = 0.95; error rate = 0.06). However, results on the
24 model for thawed stage were not satisfactory, due to the behavior of water during the freezing-
25 thawing process in both types of samples (with and without added water). For the combined
26 model, NIR failed in the classification (accuracy = 0.68; error rate = 0.32), BIA gave acceptable
27 results (accuracy = 0.72; error rate = 0.28) and TDR made a good classification (accuracy = 0.87;
28 error rate = 0.12).

29 **KEYWORDS:** Traceability, chemometrics, fish chain, added water, smart sensors.

30 1. INTRODUCTION

31 During the last years there has been a rising concern about transparency in the food supply
32 chain, defined as “access to non-distorted, factual, relevant, and timely information about
33 supply chain products” (Astill et al. 2019). Citizens’ interest in what they consume is increasing,
34 especially after several food scandals related to adulterated food, such as that in 2013 when
35 horse meat was discovered in some beef products, or the recent studies regarding the
36 mislabeling of several seafood products in Canada and Europe (Oceana Canada, 2018; Sotelo et
37 al. 2018).

38 Though in the European Union the labelling rules that enacted the mandatory Quantitative
39 Ingredients Declaration (EU, 2011) enable citizens to get comprehensive information about the
40 content and composition of food products, sometimes the details are not clear, and induce a
41 decrease in consumer’s trust. An example is the addition of water, together with salt and
42 phosphates, to compensate for the moisture losses in some food products (van Ruth et al. 2014).
43 In the case of seafood, although this procedure is allowed, an indication of the presence of
44 added water which makes up more than 5 % of the weight of the finished product must be
45 included in the label (EU, 2011). Nevertheless, this declaration is not always present, sometimes
46 due to the intention of some producers to obtain illicit economic gains, based on bringing up the
47 product weight.

48 Furthermore, non-transparent food supply chains are subjected not only to economic losses as
49 a consequence of citizens’ mistrust, but also to other inefficiencies that lead to food losses due
50 to an incorrect food processing (Parfitt et al. 2010). As stated by Astill et al. (2019), achieving
51 transparency along the food supply chain is difficult due to its complexity and the lack of data
52 connection that sometimes exist at each link of the chain. However, in recent years, there has
53 been an effort to implement digital solutions to virtualize food supply chains and save and
54 connect the information islands along the different stakeholders. An example is the work

55 presented by Verdow et al. (2016), who proposed the use of internet of things (IoT) technologies
56 to virtualize food supply chains, specifically for the fish supply chain. In any case, to upload and
57 connect the different links of the chain, objective information needs to be provided, which can
58 be achieved through smart sensors. Smart sensors, understood as non-destructive technologies,
59 coupled with data analysis, may facilitate the information collection and sharing along the whole
60 supply chain, allowing the stakeholders to have information in real time.

61 In the last years, there has been an increase in the use of non-destructive technologies to
62 improve the transparency along the fish supply chain. Qin et al., (2020) described the detection
63 of the substitution of high-priced fish species with inexpensive alternatives and the mislabeling
64 of frozen-thawed fish fillets as fresh using hyperspectral imaging. Velioglu et al., (2015) used
65 Raman spectroscopy with similar purposes. Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) has also been
66 proposed as a method for the authentication of the origin of fish (Masoum et al., 2007) or to
67 control the quality of the lipids (Vidal et al., 2012). Other techniques, as electrical impedance,
68 have been used to detect the freshness estimation of fish (Zhao et al., 2017).

69 In this work, three hand-held non-destructive technologies were used, coupled with the
70 classifier partial least squares discriminant analysis (PLS-DA), as rapid tools to detect water
71 addition in an added-value seafood product, such as tuna. The three technologies were:
72 bioelectrical impedance analysis (BIA), near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopy and time-domain
73 reflectometry (TDR). They are all portable and based on different principles. BIA measures the
74 impedance (resistance and reactance) of a current passed through an organism or tissue. This
75 technique is based on the impedance differences between fat and fat-free tissues (Cox &
76 Hartman, 2005). The resistance value is sensible to changes in water content due to water, as
77 opposite to fat, is a good conductor of electricity. On the contrary, the reactance value is related
78 with the intracellular and the extracellular water volume (Zaniboni-Filho et al., 2015). NIR
79 spectroscopy is a technique based on the absorption of electromagnetic radiation at

80 wavelengths between 780 nm and 2500 nm by functional groups (Huang, et al., 2008). All
81 organic bonds have absorption bands in the NIR region, and especially water shows a strong
82 signal in this part of the spectrum. Samples with high water contents are strongly dominated by
83 the water signal (Büning-Pfaue, 2003). Finally, TDR is based on the measurement of the
84 product's dielectric properties in the microwave region as a function of frequency (100 MHz–10
85 GHz). As water has an intrinsic electric dipole moment, its dynamics is influenced by an external
86 oscillating electric field in the range of microwaves. This affects the dielectric properties of the
87 medium. Thus, changes in the amount of water in the muscle are expected to be detected by
88 this technology (Kent & Daschner, 2009). Hence, the three techniques are sensitive to the water
89 signal, which make them suitable for measuring added water.

90 Regarding BIA, there have been some recent efforts to detect the added water in other
91 foodstuffs such as pork products (Leng et al., 2019). NIR spectroscopy has been used for
92 adulterants detection in several kinds of food (Khodabux et al., 2007; Reis et al., 2017; Ghidini
93 et al., 2021), however, up to authors' knowledge it is the first time that this technique is used
94 for added water detection in tuna. In the case of the TDR, Mendes et al. (2018) confirmed that
95 changes in the amount of water in octopus affected the dielectric spectrum, so this technique
96 showed the potential to quantify the added water in foodstuff.

97 Therefore, the main objective of this study is to compare the performance of the above
98 presented three non-destructive technologies, using a PLS-DA classifier, to detect water addition
99 in tuna, in order to give seafood processors, retailers, HORECA sector, etc., rapid tools to check
100 the quality in real time and improve the consumers' trust and the traceability of the chain. Since
101 the product can be purchased unfrozen or thawed in the market, in the present work
102 classification models were built for the unfrozen stage, the thawed stage and both unfrozen and
103 thawed stages, to find out which technique is more appropriate in each case.

104 **2. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

105 **2.1 RAW MATERIAL, PROCESSING, AND SAMPLING**

106 **2.1.1 Sample preparation**

107 Loins from bigeye tuna (*Thunnus obesus*) captured in the FAO 34 fishing area, near Madeira
108 Island (Portugal) and purchased from a local supplier in July 2018 and in July 2019, were used in
109 this study. The size of the tuna loins was between 3.0 and 8.3 Kg, depending on the year.

110 A total of eleven dorsal and ventral loins (seven in 2018 and four in 2019) were sectioned in
111 portions of approximately 500 g weight. Tuna portions were randomly distributed between the
112 control and the five treated samples group, assuring that each treatment had samples from both
113 dorsal and ventral loins, to reduce individual variability. During sample preparation, tuna
114 samples were kept in refrigerated conditions (3 ± 1 °C), covered with clinging film to avoid
115 dehydration.

116 Since salt, phosphates mixtures and protein hydrolysates are the most frequently used additives
117 in the industry, five different solutions were used for water addition: A (3 % salt); B (3 % salt + 3
118 % polyphosphates); C (3 % salt + 5 % polyphosphates); D (3 % salt + 5 % hydrolysate, prepared
119 in house from four-spot megrim (*Lepidorhombus boschii*); and E (polyphosphate commercial
120 solution Pescamine 150). Also, some samples remained without added water (control group).
121 Tuna samples were manually processed with a 10 % weight injection of the five different
122 solutions (see Figure 1 of the supplementary material). Afterwards, samples were kept for 3 h
123 in refrigerated conditions (3 ± 1 °C) covered with clinging film for stabilization.

124 BIA, NIR and TDR measurements were taken in added and non-added water samples (see Figure
125 2 of the supplementary material). These samples are referred to as *unfrozen samples*.
126 Afterwards, samples were vacuum packed and frozen. Freezing was done in a slow freezer
127 (freezing rate 0.01 °C/min) at -20 °C, for 40 hours, being the temperature achieved in the center
128 of the samples of -12 ± 1 °C. The intention was to challenge the methods with the conditions of

129 a possible imperfect freezing procedure performed by seafood processors and restaurants,
130 which are usually not equipped with fast freezing units, as they will be the potential users of
131 these technologies. Internal sample temperature was monitored using an insertion probe digital
132 thermometer, inserted 3-5 cm into the tissue. Furthermore, samples were placed next to each
133 other but not in overlapping layers, to assure a uniform freezing process among samples.
134 Afterwards, samples were thawed at 3 ± 1 °C. These samples are referred to as *thawed samples*.
135 After thawing, BIA, NIR and TDR measurements were taken in all samples and all tuna samples
136 (vacuum packed) were kept frozen. Later, a 250 g section of each 500 g tuna portion was cut
137 and minced for the determination of proximate composition (e.g. moisture, protein and fat
138 contents).

139 **2.1.2 Chemicals and reagents**

140 All chemicals and reagents used were analytical grade of the highest purity and supplied by
141 Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). Salt (NaCl) of food grade was used to prepare the solutions.
142 Pescamine 150 (E451, E450, E452, E339) is a mixture composed of sodium phosphates and it
143 was prepared according to the manufacturer's indications (Vaessen-Schoemaker, Deventer, The
144 Netherlands).

145 **2.2 PROXIMATE COMPOSITION: MOISTURE, PROTEIN AND FAT CONTENTS**

146 Moisture content was determined by standard gravimetric analysis (AOAC, 2005), while crude
147 protein content was determined by the Dumas combustion method according to Saint-Denis &
148 Goupy (2004) in a LECO FP-528 protein/nitrogen analyzer (LECO Corp., St Joseph, MI, USA)
149 calibrated with ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA). Moisture and protein contents were
150 determined in all the tuna portions in duplicate.

151 Fat content was determined according to the method described by Bligh & Dyer (1959). Briefly,
152 minced tuna samples (2 g) were homogenized with 4 mL of methanol and 2 mL of

153 dichloromethane in a Polytron homogenizer (10000 rpm, 1 min). Then, 2 mL of dichloromethane
154 and 2 mL of water were added and further homogenized in the same conditions. After
155 centrifugation (3000 rpm, 5 °C, 10 min), the organic phase was separated, and a second
156 extraction was performed. Both recovered organic phases were mixed, filtered with anhydrous
157 sodium sulphate and the solvent was evaporated, being the fat content determined by weight.
158 Fat content was determined in two of each control and added water samples in duplicate.

159 2.3 NON-DESTRUCTIVE METHODS

160 Since samples were kept in refrigerated conditions (3 ± 1 °C), even after thawing, the
161 temperature can be considered nearly constant, and its influence can be neglected.

162 *Figure 1. (a) BIA 101 Anniversary device with modified electrode set; (b) BIA electrode placement on the*
163 *sample; (c) NIR Spectrometer MicroNIR OnSite; (d) NIR applicator placement on the sample; (e) TDR*
164 *equipment RFQ-Scan® Sequid analyser; (f) RFQ-Scan® probe placement on the sample.*

165

166 2.3.1 Bioelectrical impedance analysis

167 Bioimpedance data were collected with a BIA 101 Anniversary (Akern SRL) (BIA from now on)
168 with a tetrapolar electrode device, which was modified into a dipolar electrode cable set by the

169 manufacturer company. This modification was required by the geometry of the sample and does
170 not affect the results, according to the manufacturer's experience. The resulting electrode pair
171 was attached to a PVC plate to keep a fixed distance of 52 mm between the electrodes (detector
172 length) (Figure 1a). The plate with the electrodes was placed consistently in each tuna sample
173 in the center of the external side of the loin (Figure 1b). Both electrodes were introduced 1 cm
174 depth into the sampled portion. The impedance was measured when a small current (400 μ A,
175 50 kHz) was passed through it. Measurements of Resistance (R), Reactance (Xc) and Phase angle
176 (Pa) were directly collected.

177 **2.3.2 Near-infrared spectroscopy**

178 A MicroNIR OnSite (Viavi) (NIR from now on), devoted for portable rapid inspection, was used
179 as handheld equipment (Figure 1c and 1d). It has a wavelength range of 900 to 1650 nm, with
180 two integrated vacuum tungsten lamps. It works with a 128-pixel InGaAs photodiode array with
181 a spectral resolution of < 1.225 % of center wavelength (1 % typical).

182 **2.3.3 Time domain reflectometry**

183 Dielectric properties (complex permittivity) of tuna samples were measured with a Time Domain
184 Reflectometry analyzer (TDR from now on), the Sequid RFQ-Scan[®] (Sequid GmbH, Bremen,
185 Germany). The RFQ-Scan[®] system applies an ultra-wideband step signal to the material under
186 test (Schimmer & Knöchel, 2003). The time domain response of samples to an input step signal
187 applied to the sample surface via an open-ended coaxial probe was measured (Figure 1e and
188 1f).

189 Before the data analysis, all the TDR signals were pre-filtered to reduce the noise and the
190 influence of temperature, followed by an internal phase compensation (performed by air-
191 measurements). After that, a predefined section of 2.56 ns of the curve was selected and a
192 normalization of the amplitude was performed (Schimmer et al. 2009).

193 **2.4. DATA ACQUISITION**

194 Data acquisition was made in all the tuna portions in unfrozen and thawed stages, to build
195 calibrations for every stage that can be found in the market.

196 Data acquisition was different for each technology, adapted to each device's characteristics, to
197 make a representative sampling with each one. Consequently, the number of data collected with
198 each device was different (see Table 1 of the supplementary material):

- 199 ● BIA: 1 measurement per sample.
- 200 ● NIR: 8 scans per sample, acquired at different points of the tuna portions. Each scan was
201 treated later as an independent sample for the model building.
- 202 ● TDR: the average of 8 scans per sample, acquired at different points of the tuna portions.

203 The methodology used with samples in both trials (2018 and 2019) was similar, so samples from
204 2018 were used as a calibration dataset and those from 2019 were used as an independent
205 validation dataset. This division was made with the aim to create a robust model, which could
206 predict new samples from different fishing years.

207 For the calibration dataset of BIA and NIR, N = 60 unfrozen samples were measured with the
208 two technologies before being injected with the five different solutions. In the case of the TDR,
209 the 10 samples used as the control group were scanned. Afterwards, 50 out of the 60 samples
210 were injected (10 samples per solution). After the freezing-thawing process, all the samples
211 were measured again.

212 At the validation stage, N = 60 unfrozen samples were available and all of them were measured
213 as non-added water with BIA and NIR. However, TDR sensor scanned only the control group (N
214 = 20) as non-added water samples. Afterwards, 40 unfrozen samples were injected with the

215 different solutions and scanned. Then, 30 samples were sent to fast freezing, devoted to another
216 experiment, out of the scope of this paper and the remaining 30 (10 samples as control group
217 and 4 per solution) were used for the validation. These samples were thawed and scanned again,
218 having 10 non-added water samples and 20 added water samples.

219 **2.5. DATA ANALYSIS**

220 **2.5.1 Moisture/protein ratio**

221 The values of moisture/protein ratio of added water and non-added water samples were
222 calculated to evaluate whether the injection procedure was efficient. Then, the differences were
223 analyzed by means of an analysis of variance (one-way ANOVA).

224 **2.5.2 Descriptive statistics of the proximate composition data**

225 To analyze the distribution of the proximate composition of samples from different years, a
226 descriptive statistical analysis was developed. Then, an ANOVA was carried out to evaluate the
227 differences among compositions between both trials. Both analyses were developed with the
228 software Statgraphics (version 16.2.04).

229 **2.5.3 Model building and validation**

230 Before building the classification models, data were pre-processed to remove the irrelevant
231 information. For NIR and TDR data some methods were tested. First, standard normal variate
232 with or without detrend (SNVd, SNV), multiplicative scatter correction (MSC), using mean and
233 median value as references, generalized least squares weighting (GLS Weighting), probabilistic
234 quotient normalization (PQN) and external parameter orthogonalization (EPO) filter were
235 applied. After that, Savitzky-Golay's first and second derivatives, with different polynomial order
236 and windows, were tried. Finally, some combinations of all these methods were created and

237 tested. Then, data were mean centered. In the case of data from BIA, only autoscaling was
238 applied.

239 Classification models were built using the Classification toolbox (version 5.1) for Matlab R 2017b,
240 developed by Milano Chemometrics and QSAR Research group (Ballabio & Consonni, 2013). PLS-
241 DA (Sjöström et al. 1986; Ståhle & Wold, 1987) was used for classification. For the class
242 assignment, a threshold was calculated based on the Bayes theorem (Ballabio & Consonni,
243 2013).

244 PLS-DA classification models were built with data from 2018 and fitted using Venetian Blinds
245 cross-validation (CV), with 10 CV groups. Once the model was fitted, it was validated using
246 Montecarlo CV method, leaving 20 % out and 1000 iterations. Samples from 2019 were used as
247 an independent prediction dataset to test the models' robustness.

248 Three models were built:

- 249 ● **Model 1:** with data from both **unfrozen and thawed** samples.
- 250 ● **Model 2:** with data from **unfrozen** samples.
- 251 ● **Model 3:** with data from **thawed** samples.

252 The performance of the models was evaluated by means of the accuracy (the ratio of correct
253 assignments) and the error rate (calculated as 1 – arithmetic means of all class non-error rates),
254 the sensitivity (the proportion of added-water samples predicted as added-water) and the
255 specificity (the proportion of non-added water predicted as non-added water). These
256 parameters derived from the confusion matrix, and they are typically used for evaluating the
257 classification performance (Ballabio & Consonni, 2013).

258 **3. RESULTS**

259 **3.1 RESULTS ON DATA ANALYSIS**

260 **3.1.1 Moisture/protein ratio**

261 Moisture to protein ratio showed a statistically significant higher value on added-water samples
262 (ratio = 2.85) than on control samples (ratio = 2.71) ($F = 42.32$, $p = 0.00$) with a 95 % level of
263 confidence. An addition of 5 % of water would represent an increase of this ratio up to 2.93,
264 which is quite close to the one obtained in the added-water samples, which represents an
265 average water retention of 4.42 % after injection.

266 **3.1.2 Characterization of tuna samples per year**

267 Results on the characterization of the tuna proximate composition showed significant
268 differences between years in control and added water samples for protein ($F = 5.84$, $p = 0.02$)
269 and moisture ($F = 20.00$, $p = 0.00$) (Table 1). Fat presented higher values in 2019 than in 2018
270 though these differences were statistically non-significant for control samples ($F = 1.89$, $p = 0.19$)
271 and significant for the added water ones ($F = 22.56$, $p = 0.00$). The distribution of the data also
272 differed from one year to another, as shown in kurtosis and skewness values. Skewness was not
273 calculated in samples with bimodal or multimodal distribution.

274 *Table 1 Proximate composition of control and injected tuna samples*

Control samples						
Year	Protein (%)		Moisture (%)		Fat (%)	
	2018	2019	2018	2019	2018	2019
Mean	24.10 ^a	23.50 ^b	66.61 ^a	63.11 ^b	6.35 ^a	9.70 ^a
Typical deviation	1.35	0.57	5.23	2.86	4.76	4.99
Minimum	22.00	22.68	59.44	56.49	1.17	6.01
Maximum	26.01	25.43	73.26	66.78	11.43	17.88
Skewness	-0.10	1.44	-	-	-	-
Kurtosis	-1.41	2.93	-1.57	-0.68	-1.90	-0.71

Injected samples						
Year	Protein (%)		Moisture (%)		Fat (%)	
	2018	2019	2018	2019	2018	2019
Mean	23.20 ^a	22.60 ^b	68.41 ^a	61.43 ^b	5.29 ^a	11.90 ^b
Typical deviation	0.99	0.70	3.94	2.68	4.44	4.35
Minimum	21.39	21.29	61.89	57.25	0.79	4.93
Maximum	25.37	24.52	74.49	68.55	11.83	18.49
Skewness	0.20	0.59	-	0.72	-	-0.32
Kurtosis	-0.87	0.60	-1.55	0.02	-1.65	-1.04

275

276 ^a and ^b Consecutive letters mean significant differences according to ANOVA with a 95 % of confidence

277

level

278 3.2 COMPARISON OF RESULTS ON CLASSIFICATION MODELS IN BIA, NIR AND TDR

279 Results of all the models developed are displayed in Table 2.

280 *Table 2. Results on PLS-DA Models developed with the three technologies. Der1 and Der2 are the first*

281

and second derivatives of Savitzky-Golay

Pre-Processing method			LV	Accuracy	Error rate	Sensitivity	Specificity
Model 1: Unfrozen and thawed							
BIA	CV	Autoscaling	2	0.82	0.18	0.82	0.83
		Test		0.72	0.28	0.75	0.69
NIR	CV	SNV+Der2	16	0.84	0.16	0.84	0.83
		Test		0.68	0.32	0.66	0.70
TDR	CV	SNV+Der2	3	0.94	0.06	0.95	0.92
		Test		0.87	0.12	0.83	0.93
Model 2: Unfrozen							
BIA	CV	Autoscaling	2	0.88	0.12	0.86	0.90
		Test		0.73	0.28	0.70	0.75
NIR	CV	SNV+Der2	11	0.79	0.22	0.74	0.83
		Test		0.71	0.29	0.72	0.71
TDR	CV	SNV+Der2	4	0.97	0.05	0.98	0.91
		Test		0.95	0.06	0.97	0.90
Model 3: Thawed							
BIA	CV	Autoscaling	2	0.64	0.30	0.61	0.79
		Test		0.40	0.45	0.10	1.00
NIR	CV	Der2	9	0.86	0.15	0.87	0.83
		Test		0.51	0.55	0.62	0.28
TDR	CV	Der1	4	0.97	0.03	0.98	0.97
		Test		0.67	0.50	1.00	0.00

282

283 The three technologies showed acceptable results in the model with unfrozen samples (Model
284 2), with similar accuracy values for BIA and NIR: 0.73 and 0.71, respectively in the test set. They
285 also presented similar results on sensitivity (0.70 and 0.72, respectively) and specificity (0.75 and
286 0.71, respectively) and error rates of 0.28 and 0.29 accordingly in the test set. Nevertheless, NIR
287 showed a higher level of complexity in the model with 11 latent variables (LV), compared to that
288 shown by TDR, with only 4 LV. It also had a high accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity and low
289 error rate (0.95, 0.97 and 0.90, 0.06, respectively in the test set).

290 However, when including thawed samples in the models, the three technologies showed
291 different behaviors. On Model 1, which had unfrozen and thawed data, NIR presented lower
292 accuracy and higher error rates than the other two technologies (accuracy = 0.68; error rate =
293 0.32 vs 0.72 and 0.28 in BIA and 0.87 and 0.12 in TDR). In this case, the best results were found
294 in TDR with the highest ability of predicting added water samples (0.83 of sensitivity) and non-
295 added water samples (0.93 specificity). In any case, all the technologies failed in predicting new
296 samples in the model composed by only thawed samples (Model 3).

297 In all the cases NIR models were the most complex, since they presented the largest amount of
298 LV, with 16, 11 and 9 for Model 1, 2 and 3, respectively. BIA models had the lowest complexity,
299 since they only had 2 LV (although it was not possible to add more, since the sensor only gives
300 3 variables). TDR models presented less complexity than NIR, with 3, 4 and 4 LV for Models 1, 2
301 and 3, respectively.

302 **4. DISCUSSION**

303 **4.1 MOISTURE/PROTEIN RATIO**

304 Moisture/protein ratio has been employed as an indicator of water addition in seafood products
305 (Mendes et al. 2017). As a reference value in tuna, a ratio of 3.07 was observed in frozen *Thunnus*
306 *obesus* (Peng et al. 2013). Other tuna species, such as *Thunnus alalunga*, showed a ratio of 2.56
307 in fillets. By contrast, *Thunnus thynnus* presented higher values, which depended on the origin
308 of the fish: farmed tuna showed a moisture/protein ratio of 2.89, while the ratio for wild tuna
309 was 3.02 (Topic Popovic et al. 2012).

310 In this experiment, the moisture/protein ratio obtained was 2.71 for non-added water and 2.85
311 for added water samples, a lower value than the one expected according to the tuna references
312 and the values observed in the literature. Due to the high variability of species, a wide range in
313 this ratio is expected in seafood products; in fact, previous works analyzing commercial chilled

314 seafood have described that the lowest values were about 3.3 in salmon, a fatty fish, and the
315 highest, in panga fish, a lean fish with a ratio of 6.9 (van Ruth et al. 2014).

316 In the tuna added water samples, the limit of a 5 % of weight increment, from which added
317 water must be indicated on the label (EU, 2011), was not exceeded (the average water retention
318 obtained was 4.42 %). Thus, the classification models can detect added water even if the
319 injection does not exceed the legal limit. It is expected that the values for all models would
320 improve in the case of a more efficient injection, with higher quantities of fluid.

321 **4.2 COMPARISON OF THE PERFORMANCE OF THE MODELS DEVELOPED WITH EACH NON-** 322 **DESTRUCTIVE TECHNOLOGY**

323 Even though each non-destructive technology is based on different principles, the three of them
324 agree that the best results to discriminate between non-added and added water samples were
325 offered by the model with unfrozen samples (Model 2). Models that include thawed samples
326 (Model 1 and 3) had different performances according to the technology used. This may be due
327 to the phenomena that happens during the freezing-thawing process and the sensitivity of each
328 technology to it. As it is known, most of the water molecules in fish muscle can be considered as
329 bound to the molecular surfaces of tissue components such as proteins (Kent & Daschner, 2009).
330 During freezing the myofibrillar cells (myocytes) shrink, causing liquid leak out of the cells (Bello
331 et al. 1981; Hurling & Mcarthur, 1996) and formation of ice crystals throughout the fish muscle,
332 both inside myocytes and in the extracellular space (Fennema, 1975). However, the freezing
333 conditions affect the location and size of the ice crystals (Howgate, 1979). Particularly, during
334 slow freezing the growth of big extracellular ice crystals is supported by the water that migrates
335 from inside the myocytes, leaving them partially dehydrated (Kolbe & Kramer, 2007).
336 Additionally, as water is frozen out as pure ice crystals, there is an increase in the concentration
337 of compounds in the unfrozen portion, promoting the denaturation of myofibrillar proteins with
338 a consequent decrease in their water holding capacity. The denaturation of proteins leads to the

339 release of liquid water (Kent & Daschner, 2009). Also, breakdown of cell-wall structure leads to
340 release of solutes into the intracellular region (Kent et al. 2000). Later, when the fish is thawed,
341 the melting of extracellular ice crystals incorporating both the native extracellular water and the
342 water no longer bound to the muscle denatured proteins are converted to free water. This free
343 water does not permeate back to the muscle, instead drains away as drip loss, affecting this
344 change furthermore the results of control samples, expressed with a reduction of the differences
345 with the added water samples, with the consequent decrease in their water holding capacity.

346 The effect of the explained process and other freezing-thawing consequences, like induced
347 changes in interactions between water and proteins, may justify the differences between non-
348 added and added water tuna samples in the case of Model 1 (in BIA and TDR) and Model 2 (in
349 the three technologies), and a lower relative difference between added water and control
350 samples, causing the inability of all the sensors to predict new samples in Model 3.

351 The practical consequences of the obtained results ~~these results~~ are that only BIA and TDR are
352 the recommended technologies when there is a mixture of samples (unfrozen and thawed), as
353 seen, in the case of Model 1. The three technologies are suitable when only unfrozen samples
354 are available (as seen in Model 2) and none of them would give good results when only thawed
355 samples are present (Model 3). Therefore, it is necessary to assure if tuna has gone through a
356 freezing process or not before trying to detect added water. Different studies have used rapid
357 tools to detect frozen and thawed samples in a rapid way (Uddin & Okazaki, 2004; Cheng et al.,
358 2015; Velioglu et al., 2015; Nieto-Ortega et al., 2022). However, increasing the number of
359 samples in order to strengthen the calibration could improve the method to determine added
360 water samples with NIR in unfrozen and thawed samples (Model 1) and in the case of thawed
361 fish with the three technologies (Model 3).

362 **4.2.1 BIA**

363 BIA is a technology that measures the impedance differences between fat and fat-free tissues.

364 The loadings corresponding to the first latent variable (LV1) of the different models (Figure 2)

365 show that the three variables recorded by BIA (R, Xc and Pa) have a similar influence in Model

366 1, while in Models 2 and 3, R is the most relevant to discriminate between non-added and added

367 water samples. Thus, the different performance of the models can be fundamentally explained

368 by R. This variable is sensible to changes in water content, which is a good conductor of

369 electricity. It is directly related with the extracellular liquid and the concentration of electrolytes

370 (more electrolyte concentration reduces the R); therefore, the addition of a solution with

371 electrolytes (salts) in a sample produces a reduction of R. These differences, although not

372 significant due to the high variability within groups, are more noticeable in the unfrozen stage

373 and explain the better performance of Model 2, which only includes unfrozen samples.

374 In the case of thawed samples, the differences in all BIA parameters (R, Xc and Pa) between

375 added and non-added water samples become negligible. The low performance of Model 3,

376 constructed with data from thawed samples, is in accordance with a previous study (Cox, 2015),

377 and could be related to the effect mentioned in section 4.2. The addition of different solutions

378 has been reported to improve frozen seafood quality by reducing drip loss, mainly because they

379 are able to increase bound water (Lemos & Gonçalves, 2019), but in this study, the differences

380 in the drip loss and in BIA variables between added and non-added water samples are not

381 significant (data not shown), which may indicate that the injection is not able to improve the

382 water retention when the freezing-thawing process is imperfect.

383 *Figure 2. Loadings for Latent Variable 1 (LV1) of the BIA classification models. (a). Loadings of Model 1*

384 *(unfrozen + thawed samples); (b). Loadings of Model 2 (unfrozen samples); (c). Loadings of Model 3*

385 *(thawed samples)*

386

387 4.2.2 NIR

388 NIR spectroscopy is a technique based on the absorption of electromagnetic radiation between
 389 780 nm and 2500 nm by functional groups (Huang, et al., 2008). It is known that water signal has
 390 a strong effect in the NIR spectrum and thus, it must be considered carefully (Büning-Pfaue,
 391 2003), since they might be giving blurring information. In the present case, the added solutions
 392 were composed of water and electrolytes (salts). However, salt cannot be detected
 393 straightforwardly with NIR spectroscopy, but it needs to be done using the effect on hydrogen
 394 bonds or when salt is part of organic complexes (Büning-Pfaue, 2003).

395 Loadings for LV1 and latent variable 2 (LV2) show that the absorption bands encompassed
 396 between 1125 nm and 1435 nm have a huge influence on the three models, and the three of
 397 them present absorption peaks close to the main water absorption bands: 970 nm, 1200 nm and
 398 1450 nm, with small shifts (Figure 3) (Clevers et al., 2008). These shifts may be due to the
 399 electrolytes of the different solutions that may cause changes in height, width and position of
 400 the water absorbance bands (Laub-Ekgreen et al 2018). Nevertheless, models containing thawed
 401 samples (Model 1 and 3) present differences with respect to the model built only with unfrozen
 402 samples (Model 2). Models 1 and 3 show a more explained variance in latent variable 2 (LV2)
 403 (38.17 % and 63.95 %, respectively) than in LV1 (14.7 % and 24.45 %, respectively) (Figure 3 a1,
 404 a2, c1, c2). On the contrary, Model 2 has the highest explained variance in LV1 (65.29 %) (Figure
 405 3 b1). In PLS techniques the first LV does not necessarily retain the highest explained variance
 406 and may be due to a perfect linear between data projections (Kramer, 1998).

407 Model 2 presents a high contribution of the region encompassed between 1125 nm and 1390
408 nm in LV1 (Figure 3 b1). A similar region, from 1100 nm to 1300 nm was found by Laub-Ekgreen
409 et al. (2018) as the one giving the highest positive correlation with salt content. Thus, the peaks
410 provided by the LV1 of Model 2 may suggest that this model is detecting water together with
411 the electrolytes from the added solutions.

412 Model 1 shows peaks with a alternating profile at 1075 nm (negative) and at 1156 nm (positive)
413 in LV1 (Figure 3 a1). The 1075 nm peak may be related to the O-H of the second overtone and
414 the peak at 1156 nm could be related to the second overtone C-H stretch, which corresponds to
415 lipid information (Cheng & Sun, 2017). LV2 of Model 2 (Figure 3 b2) also presents a similar profile
416 at similar wavelengths. The different signs of both peaks suggests that they are balanced and
417 that the model may be using the evolution of water/lipid relation. During the thawing process,
418 the associated drip loss leaves samples with less water and, therefore, a higher percentage of
419 the other fish components such as lipids.

420 *Figure 3. Loadings corresponding to LV1 and LV2 of NIR classification models. (a1). (a2) – Loadings of*
421 *Model 1 (unfrozen and thawed samples); (b1). (b2) – Loadings of Model 2 (unfrozen samples); (c1). (c2) –*
422 *Loadings of Model 3 (thawed samples)*

423

424 **4.2.3 TDR**

425 Being water the major constituent of food and a molecule with an electric dipole moment, the
 426 behavior of water molecules in the tissues and its interaction with electric fields have an effect
 427 on the microwave dielectric spectrum (Daschner & Knöchel, 2005). As an expression of this
 428 behavior, injection of tuna showed an impact on the dielectric properties and in the TDR signal,
 429 namely a decrease on the signal intensity with the increase on the water content (see Figure 3

430 of the supplementary material). This is also aligned with previous studies performed by
431 Fulladosa et al. (2013) in cured ham.

432 Models 1 and 2 (with unfrozen samples) have good performance in the discrimination between
433 non-added and added water samples, while TDR signal fails in the prediction of added water
434 when only data from thawed samples were used (Model 3). Loadings of the three models show
435 that the variables with the highest contribution are around 0.55 ns and 1.17 ns (Figure 4). Model
436 1 presents several peaks among this region in both LV1 and LV2, while Model 3 only has two
437 variables that influence the model, at 0.70 ns and 0.80 ns, again in both LV. The range between
438 0.60 ns and 0.80 ns has been related to changes in water content, while the region between 1.00
439 ns and 2.3 ns is expected to be related to the salt content (Fulladosa et al., 2013). The absence
440 of variables below 0.70 ns and above 0.80 ns in loadings of Model 3 suggests that the freezing-
441 thawing process has an effect not only in the water content but also in the salt distribution.

442 *Figure 4. Loadings corresponding to LV1 and LV2 of TDR classification models. (a1). (a2) – Loadings of*
443 *Model 1 (unfrozen and thawed samples); (b1). (b2) – Loadings of Model 2 (unfrozen samples); (c1). (c2) –*
444 *Loadings of Model 3 (thawed samples)*

445

446 The sensitivity of the TDR system responses to changes in the amount of muscle water and the
 447 effect of freezing and thawing on the release of intracellular and extracellular water and
 448 therefore, on the interactions between water and protein in the muscle of tuna may justify this
 449 behavior. In opposition to the differences found between unfrozen added water and control
 450 samples, freezing and thawing induced a non-proportional release of water and decreased the

451 time-dependent signal differences between samples to a level not differentiable by the TDR
452 system, as shown by Model 3 results.

453 **5. CONCLUSIONS**

454 This study evidences the possibilities and differences between the three non-destructive
455 technologies studied (BIA, NIR and TDR), coupled with a PLS-DA classifier, in the detection of
456 added water in the selected matrix (tuna). All technologies demonstrate capacities to distinguish
457 between added and non-added water samples in at least one of the studied stages (unfrozen,
458 thawed or a combination of both). The three technologies worked well in the discrimination of
459 added and non-added water samples in the unfrozen stage (Model 2) and all of them failed when
460 only thawed samples were considered (Model 3), due to the phenomena that happen to water
461 in tissues subjected to slow freezing and thawing processes. BIA and TDR can be used to predict
462 if tuna was processed with added water in unfrozen and even in a mixture of unfrozen and
463 thawed samples (using Model 1). In the case of NIR, it is necessary to ensure that samples were
464 not frozen. After that, Model 2 can be used to discriminate between added and non-added
465 water samples.

466 The implementation of these non-destructive techniques in the food industry would allow the
467 control of the supply chain at an early stage. Also, the three technologies may be useful in
468 different stages of the food chain (i.e. seafood processors, retailers, HORECA sector) as rapid
469 and non-destructive quality control tools for routine analysis, in order to detect, in a rapid way,
470 added water in tuna samples. Nowadays, there is a lack of non-destructive and rapid tools to
471 control this mislabeling problem. Thus, these technologies could help to collect rapid and
472 objective data that may lead to increase citizens' trust. The findings of this study could be used
473 for control purposes using these models for classification, ensuring reproducibility and accuracy.
474 However, the limitations of the technologies regarding thawed samples must be considered,
475 since the models did not work if there are only samples in this stage. Future studies are

476 necessary to solve this problem, in order to detect the water addition in all types of
477 commercialized samples.

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649 Supplementary material:

650 *Table 1. Number of samples measured with BIA, NIR and RFQ-Scan® during the calibration and validation*
 651 *studies of water addition detection in tuna.*

Sensor	Unfrozen (Calibration)		Thawed (Calibration)	
	Non-injected	Injected	Non-injected	Injected
	N _{samples}	N _{samples}	N _{samples}	N _{samples}
BIA	60	50	10	50
NIR	60	50	10	50
TDR	10	50	10	50
Sensor	Unfrozen (Validation)		Thawed (Validation)	
	Non-injected	Injected	Non-injected	Injected
	N _{samples}	N _{samples}	N _{samples}	N _{samples}
BIA	60	40	10	20
NIR	60	40	10	20
TDR	20	40	10	20

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654 *Figure 1. Injection of tuna portions.*

655 *Figure 2: Scheme indicating the BIA, NIR and TDR measurements during the trial for the*
656 *calibration and validation study of water addition detection in tuna samples (of 500 g each).*

657 *Figure 3. TDR signal in non-injected and injected samples (unfrozen and thawed).*

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